

Protein Biomarkers: In Life and After Life

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ABSTRACT

Living humans, elicit certain specific biochemical parameters characteristic of their physiological state. Similarly, various changes in the chemical composition occur in the body after death. Some of these biochemical parameters can be used as biomarkers both for disease diagnosis as well as for gaining a deep understanding of the changes during post-mortem.

Biomarkers thus help in understanding the physiological state of an individual, the progression of disease, the effectiveness of various treatments that are targeted to cure the disease, the prognosis of such diseases as osteoarthritis, post-polio syndrome, ovarian cancer, osteosarcoma, alzheimer's disease etc. Post-mortem degradation products such as amino acids, hypoxanthine, volatile organic compounds and various proteins are some biomarkers that are used to understand the phenomenon of post-mortem.

Keyword: Biomarkers; Proteins; Disease; Postmortem; Decomposition.

INTRODUCTION

Biomarkers include tools and technologies that can aid in understanding the prediction, cause, diagnosis, progression, regression or outcome of treatment of diseases.

They can be a means for homogenous classification of a disease and risk factors and extend our basic information about the pathogenesis of disease. They reflect the entire spectrum of disease from earliest manifestations to the terminal stages. They can be measured in biological fluids like blood, serum, cerebrospinal fluid, in tissues or even in a particular cell of interest. Biomarkers are rapidly becoming a subject of great interest in the fields of observational and analytical epidemiology, randomized clinical trials, screening and diagnosis, and prognosis of diseases.

Biomarkers can be defined in various ways:-

A biomarker or biological marker is any measurable substance in the body that can be an indicator or pathological state or a measure of response to a therapeutic intervention. (or) Biomarkers are cellular, biochemical or molecular alterations that are measurable in biological media such as human tissues, cells or fluids. (or) Biological characteristics that can be objectively measured and evaluated as an indicator of normal biological processes, pathogenic processes or pharmacological responses to a therapeutic intervention.

Types of biomarkers:

Biomarkers can be broadly divided into two groups

1. Biomarkers of exposure/ antecedent biomarkers:-

When a disease is suspected resulting from a toxic exposure, researchers wish to measure the degree of exposure. External exposure is the measured concentration of the toxin in an individual's immediate environment. Direct measurement of the alleged toxin in the air, water, soil, or food can provide accurate information regarding the "dose" of the exposure. When the toxin is identified in tissues or body fluids it becomes a biomarker for the internal dose. A biomarker that measures a "biologically effective dose" generally indicates the amount of toxin or chemical measured in the target organ or its surrogate. Most biomarkers of exposure measure antecedent factors thought to modify [increase or decrease] the risk of developing the disease investigated. The advantage of a biomarker of exposure over a history of exposure is that it estimates the actual "internal" dose of the exposure. This improves precision in the measurement of any risk factor.

By definition these antecedent biomarkers exist before the disease or the outcomes occur and are independent of other exposures. They improve the precision in the measurement of other associations, because they may be synergistic or antagonistic.

Fig 1: Disease pathway and potential impact of biomarkers
Intermediate Biomarkers-

Some biomarkers represent direct steps in the causal pathway of a disease and are therefore strongly related to disease. Others are related in some indirect way to the cause. There are numerous possibilities to consider. A biomarker could be dependent on another known or unknown factor to cause disease. Thus, it is not the only determinant but it is in the causal pathway and remains strongly related to the disease.

2. Biomarker of disease:-

These are used in screening, diagnosis and monitoring of disease progression. Biomarkers depict signs that enable earlier diagnosis or allow for the outcome of interest to be determined at a more early stage of disease. Blood, urine, and cerebrospinal fluid provide the necessary biological information for the diagnosis. In these conditions, biomarkers are used as an indicator of a biological factor that represents either a subclinical manifestation, stage of the disorder, or a surrogate manifestation of the disease. The potential uses of this class of biomarkers include: 1) identification of individuals destined to become affected or who are in the "preclinical" stages of the illness, 2) reduction in disease heterogeneity in clinical trials or epidemiologic studies, 3) reflection of the natural history of disease encompassing the phases of induction, latency and detection, and 4) target for a clinical trial. [1]

VARIABILITY IN BIOMARKERS:

Although biomarkers have numerous advantages, variability is a concern. Variability applies regardless of whether the biomarker represents an exposure or effect modifier, a surrogate of the disease, or an indication of susceptibility. Interindividual variability can result from the amount of an external exposure or from the way a putative toxin is metabolized. For example, individuals exposed to the same chemical might differ in their ability (or inability) to metabolize the agent, or they may have experienced different types of exposures (in the field as compared with in the office). Intraindividual variability is usually related to laboratory errors or other conditions, or exposures unique to the individual. Group variability is also encountered, but this is often the desired outcome of a study. [1]

Biomarkers are of various types:

1. **Anthropomorphic Biomarkers-** are of the body shape/form.
E.g. Body mass index.
2. **Cellular Biomarkers-** are whole cells.
E.g. Cancer cells identified by Pap test.

3. **Biochemical Biomarkers-** Are substances or products of chemical reactions in living organisms. E.g. Cholesterol and bilirubin.
4. **Genomic Biomarkers-** Are variants in the DNA sequence or in the transcription level.
E.g. HER2 or RNA.
5. **Physiological Biomarkers-** Are body processes.
E.g. Systolic Blood Pressure.
6. **Proteomic Biomarkers-** are variants in protein sequences, protein levels in a given tissue, protein interactions and enzyme activities.
7. **Structural Biomarkers-** Are anatomical structures. E.g. Hippocampus or are lesions
E.g. Atherosclerosis Plaque.

PROTEIN BIOMARKERS

Proteins are more diverse and therefore potentially more informative and suitable as biomarkers. Protein biomarkers are produced as an effect of the disease, exposure to toxic agents, drug administration and are good indicators of the physiological state.

The complex composition of protein in blood, post-translational modifications, low relative abundance, sequence variations, and difficulties associated with the development of high-affinity detection agents render the discovery and development of new protein-based biomarkers challenging and expensive.

When choosing a biomarker for study, its reproducibility and concentration, high enough to allow for its consistent detection and evaluation should be considered.

Proteins as Disease Biomarkers

Proteins have extensively been studied as biomarkers in various disease conditions, where their study has been useful for researchers to gain more information about the disease, its progression and development of effective drugs. Protein biomarkers have been extensively studied in cancer, osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, renal and kidney failure, osteosarcoma, transplantation etc.

In a study on **knee osteoarthritis**, [2] using serum and urine biomarkers for pain, Ishijima et.al (2011) studied a hypothesis that there is a relationship between the onset of early stage radiographically defined knee osteoarthritis pain and changes in biomarker of joint metabolism. The results suggested that changes in cartilage matrix turnover detected by molecular biomarkers may reflect changes in cartilage structure that account directly or indirectly for knee pain.

Protein biomarkers for Post-Polio Syndrome [3] has also been of interest.

Survivors of Poliomyelitis often develop increased or new symptoms decades after the acute infection, a condition called Post- Polio Syndrome (PPS).

A study undertaken by Gonzalez et.al (2009), intended to find protein biomarkers in PPS patients that could be helpful in understanding the pathogenesis of the disease and its diagnosis. Using cerebrospinal fluid, from normal as well as patients with PPS, and applying the techniques of 2 D gel electrophoresis and mass spectrometry, the investigators found 5 distinct proteins, gelsolin, hemopexin, peptidylglycine alpha amidating monooxygenase, glutathione synthetase and kallikrein 6, respectively, to be present in the CSF of patients, in comparison

with the control groups. An independent ELISA confirmed the increase of kallikrein 6, in PPS patients.

The identification and validation of early detection biomarkers highly specific to ovarian cancer, which would permit development of minimally invasive screening methods for detecting early onset of the disease, are also under study.

Current practices for early detection of ovarian cancer include transvaginal ultrasonography, biomarker analysis, or a combination of both. Biomarkers for early detection of ovarian cancer include KLK6/7, GSTT1, PRSS8, FOLR1, ALDH1, and miRNAs [4].

The liver plays a central role in metabolizing xenobiotics; therefore, it is highly susceptible to toxicity from these chemicals. Certain drugs, when taken in overdose and sometimes even when used within therapeutic range, may cause injury to the organ. Drug-induced liver injury is now a leading cause of acute liver failure.

Genetic markers used in detecting Drug Induced Liver Injury (DILI)

DILI is strongly affected by genetic predisposition, and by the polymorphisms associated with type I and II drug metabolizing enzymes. Various genetic polymorphisms in drug metabolizing enzymes and immunological mediators such as human leukocyte antigen (HLA) molecules and cytokines have been shown to correlate well with the patients' susceptibility to DILI.

The polymorphisms of these genes may be able to serve as markers to predict susceptibility of exposed individuals to DILI. Advanced technologies such as genome-wide association studies (GWAS) and highly parallelized next-generation sequencing (NextGen) are now providing new methods to explore the association between genetic predisposition and DILI. For example, a GWAS study revealed that the HLA-B*5701 genotype is a major risk factor and ST6GAL1 is a possible cofactor of an individual's vulnerability to flucloxacillin-induced DILI.

Blood biomarkers used in detecting DILI

In addition to genetic markers, histological examination and imaging, the most common tests used in the clinic are based on the concentration changes of specific molecules in different body fluids, especially blood.

Different types of blood DILI biomarkers including metabolites (8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine in urine), proteins (FL-K18/cK18 in urine), and DNA (mt/nuclear DNA fragments in plasma) have been studied in human [5].

In a comparative proteomic study between human osteosarcoma cell line (MG-63) and human osteoblastic cell line (normal), using iTRAQ-based quantitative differential LC/MS/MS technique, 342 non-redundant proteins were identified, 68 of which were differentially expressed with 1.5-fold difference, with 25 up-regulated and 43 down-regulated. Among those differential proteins, 69% were plasma membrane, which are related to the biological processes of binding, cell structure, signal transduction, cell adhesion, etc., and interaction with each other.

Of these, a plasma membrane protein CD151, showed differential expression, and its over-expression was confirmed in osteosarcoma cells using immunohistochemistry. The study further validates the presence of CD151 plasma membrane protein in patients and proposes its use as a biomarker. [7]

Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD) is an X-linked recessive disorder, which results in chronic inflammation and

severe skeletal muscle degeneration. A study performed by E. Abdel-Salam et al, evaluated the extent of muscle degeneration and regeneration, in the blood of DMD patients.

Levels of Fas and Fas L, Bax/Bcl-2 and plasma DNA fragments were measured as markers of apoptosis/ degeneration; and Cytokine tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) and growth factors namely basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) were measured as biomarkers of regeneration.

The researchers found an increase in plasma DNA fragments, Fas and Fas L. Also showed an increase in Bax mRNA concentration and a consequent decrease in the concentration of Bcl-2 protein. The regeneration biomarker TNF- α and bFGF show an increased concentration in patients, whereas VEGF concentration is decreased with respect to that in normal subjects. The study concludes that FAS/FASL and Bax/Bcl-2 are involved in muscle atrophy and degeneration in DMD patients, while the process of regeneration is unable to cope with degeneration. Also suggests the use of above mentioned biomarkers as a prognostic tool to determine disease severity, instead of the invasive technique of muscle biopsy [8].

Alzheimer's is a common form of dementia, affecting individuals all over the world and hence is a topic of extensive research. Currently diagnosis of this disease is done via clinical assessments and confirmed by post mortem brain pathology. Hence the ongoing research on Alzheimer's focuses on finding reliable biomarkers that will help in prognosis and diagnosis of the disease. So far, biomarkers in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) like A β 40, A β 42, total tau and phosphorylated tau are shown to be of diagnostic value in developed and early Alzheimer's disease. Biomarkers of AD in plasma are still a matter of study. Plasma contains very low levels of tau, which are of no use in diagnosis. Recent studies have indicated that while plasma A β 42 levels alone may not be a good biomarker for AD diagnosis; its levels are increased in early AD and changes in its level could indicate a transition from Mild Cognitive Impairment to Alzheimer's disease [9].

Myocardial Infarction is one of the major heart conditions leading to mortality in humans. Serum/blood protein biomarkers of MI are now being used for risk factor assessment or diagnosis of this condition.

Two well-known protein biomarkers in use for diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction are Creatine-Kinase-MB isoform and Cardiac Troponin. In 2000, Cardiac Troponin replaced CK-MB as the biomarker of choice for diagnosing a myocardial infarction. Troponin is a protein released from myocytes when irreversible myocardial damage occurs, and its level is dependent on size of infarct. Troponin levels peak at 12 hours, and stay elevated for 10 days or more. Another protein biomarker, Copeptin is the more stable surrogate of arginine vasopressin (AVP), with well-known effects on osmoregulation and cardiovascular homeostasis. Post Acute Myocardial Infarction, vasopressin is thought to (1) increase peripheral vasoconstrictor activity thus increasing afterload and ventricular stress; (2) increase protein synthesis in myocytes leading to hypertrophy and (3) vasoconstriction of coronary arteries. Copeptin is released in stoichiometric proportion to vasopressin and is stable and easily assayed.

Another biomarker, Heart-Type Fatty Acid Binding Protein (H-FABP) is a low molecular weight protein involved in myocardial fatty-acid metabolism. It is also found in small quantities in brain, kidney and skeletal tissue and levels can go up

in acute ischaemic strokes and intense exercise. It is rapidly released early in myocardial infarction and necrosis, into the cytosol but not used as a sole biomarker of AMI due to improper results in studies [10]

Advanced glycation end products (AGE's) is another example of biomarkers used in disease prognosis. AGE's are heterogeneous group of macromolecules that are formed by the non-enzymatic glycation of proteins, lipids and nucleic acids. AGE's are formed in the human body during the normal aging process, but their formation is accelerated during diabetes and oxidative stress. A study by Yaffe et.al suggests that higher peripheral AGE (pentosidine) concentration is associated with the risk of cognitive decline in elder adults. Increased AGE levels are also linked to age related conditions including inflammation, vascular disease and chronic kidney disease [11].

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small noncoding RNA molecules that can modulate gene expression in a wide range of biological process. By binding to the target messenger RNA (mRNA). Seed sequence complementarity of ~7 base pairs enables miRNA to bind to the target mRNA. The direct interaction of the seed sequence with their target mRNAs can result in the inhibition of translation or in the reduction in the stability of the mRNA, both of which can result in decreased expression of the target protein. Most miRNA sequences are conserved across species; the expression of some miRNAs is specific to tissues or biological stages; and the level of miRNAs can be easily measured by quantitative PCR, which allows for high-precision signal amplification. Thus, detection of miRNA can be sensitive, predictive, specific, robust, translatable, and noninvasive, all characteristics of the ideal biomarker. miRNA, like proteins, have tissue specific expression patterns.

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) belong to a class of small non protein coding RNA molecules of 18 to 22 nucleotides in length that negatively regulate gene expression. Their small size makes them less prone to degradation, making them a useful molecular tool for forensic body fluid identification. Using microarray technique, all 5 body fluids, namely blood, semen, menstrual blood, saliva and vaginal secretion, could be clearly differentiated from each other, based on miRNA expression.

Time- wise stability of miRNA markers was also determined in blood and semen. Samples collected at the start of the study were aged for a period of 1 year, under lab conditions. Using quantitative RT-PCR technique, miRNA expression profiles obtained showed similarity with those obtained at the start; also absolute expression levels did not diminish in old samples [17].

All the researches considered present a good example for the use of biomarkers in prognosis and diagnosis of various diseases. The levels of various disease biomarkers when monitored accurately will aide in proper diagnosis and use of proper treatments.

BIOMARKERS: AFTER LIFE

Biomarkers are not only of great value when studied with respect to disease prognosis or diagnosis in living human beings, but also are of great value in post mortem analysis. Biomarkers can provide a great deal of information regarding the process of post mortem changes taking place in the human body, under various conditions.

The human body starts to decay in about 4 minutes after death. The decomposition process is affected by many factors: method and time of burial, corpse-specific characteristics (weight, sex, age, cause of death) and conditions of the resting place

(temperature, pH, insect and carnivore activity, moisture, and soil type). Microbiology plays a major role in decomposition: protozoa, fungi, aerobic and anaerobic bacteria are involved.

The onset of decay is governed by a process called autolysis – or self-digestion. As cells of the body are deprived of oxygen, carbon dioxide in the blood increases, pH decreases and wastes accumulate which poison the cells. Concomitantly, unchecked cellular enzymes (lipases, proteases, amylases, etc.) begin to dissolve the cells from the inside out, eventually causing them to rupture, and releasing nutrient-rich fluids.

Autolysis usually does not become visually apparent for a few days. It is first observed by the appearance of fluid filled blisters on the skin and skin slippage where large sheets of skin slough off the body. Meanwhile, the body has acclimated to ambient temperature (*algor mortis*), blood has settled in the body causing discoloration of the skin (*livor mortis*) and cellular cytoplasm has gelled due to increased acidity (*rigor mortis*). After enough cells have ruptured, nutrient-rich fluids become available and the process of putrefaction begins.

Putrefaction is the destruction of the soft tissues of the body by the action of micro-organisms (bacteria, fungi and protozoa) and results in the catabolism of tissue into gases, liquids and simple molecules. Usually, the first visible sign of putrefaction is a greenish discoloration of the skin due to the formation of sulfhaemoglobin in settled blood. The process progresses into distension of tissues due to the formation of various gases.

Saponification (the formation of soap from fat under high pH conditions) or adipocere formation typically occurs after the onset of putrefaction in warm, moist, environments and is seen as deposits of a yellowish-white, greasy, wax-like substance. Adipocere develops as the result of fat hydrolysis with the release of fatty acids. Mummification is typically the end result of tissue, usually skin, with no nutritional value, which has survived the active decay process and is formed by the dehydration or desiccation of the tissue. Remaining skin is converted into a leathery or parchment-like sheet which clings to bone. Mummification most commonly develops in conditions of dry heat or in areas that have very low humidity, such as in arctic regions or deserts.

Bone goes through yet another complex process called diagenesis. Diagenesis is a natural process that serves to alter the proportions of organic (collagen) and inorganic components (hydroxyapatite, calcium, magnesium) of bone exposed to environmental conditions, especially moisture. [12]. The study of post mortem decomposition is of great use in forensic investigations, where the stage of decomposition helps in determining the time of death. Various biomarkers have been studied or developed that are of great use in forensic investigations.

The study of mammalian soft tissue decomposition is an emerging area in forensic science, with a major focus being the use of various chemical and biological methods to study the fate of human remains in the environment.

Decomposition of mammalian soft tissue, depends on environmental conditions and physiological factors and will proceed until complete disintegration of the tissue occurs. An understanding of this process is extremely important for investigations of suspicious deaths as it complicates determination of cause of death and makes the estimation of postmortem interval very difficult. The major stages of decomposition involve complex reactions which result in the chemical breakdown of the body's main constituents; lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates. As

decomposition proceeds, these macromolecules degrade to their structural components which include amino acids, fatty acids, and glucose. Soft tissue decomposition can be studied using chromatographic as well as non-chromatographic techniques.

The process of soft tissue decomposition results in a release of nutrients into the soil surrounding a cadaver. A proportion of these nutrients result from the release of nitrogen-containing compounds within the body, which include proteins, peptides, amino acids, and amines. These nitrogenous compounds have the ability to react with ninhydrin. It has been hypothesized that the decomposition of a body would result in an increase in ninhydrin reactive nitrogen (NRN) and may provide a new technique for identifying grave soil (i.e. soil associated with a decomposing cadaver).

Adipocere, a postmortem decomposition product may be found directly on decomposed remains or in the surrounding soil environment, especially in burials. Spectroscopic techniques have also been applied to forensic decomposition studies to identify fatty acid concentrations indicative of adipocere formation. The use of infrared spectroscopy as a qualitative tool for determining the lipid profile of soft tissue has been well documented.

In the early stages of postmortem interval, one of the most widely reported biochemical method to estimate postmortem interval is the determination of potassium ion (K⁺) and hypoxanthine (Hx) concentrations in vitreous humor.

The vitreous humor refers to the fluid that fills the vitreous body (or posterior chamber) of the eye. Its potential usefulness for postmortem chemical analysis results from it being anatomically confined and thus somewhat 'protected' and preserved for longer time periods from bacterial contamination, enzymatic activity and putrefactive changes. It has also been stated that vitreous humor has advantages for chemical analysis for biomarkers compared to the use of blood and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) due to accessibility, ease of sampling, less susceptibility than blood to rapid chemical changes and relative independence from environmental influences.

Hypoxanthine (Hx) is a degradation product of adenosine and is elevated due to hypoxia prior to death. Hypoxanthine has previously been analysed by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with applications generally in the pharmaceutical and medical fields. The potential for the use of vitreous Hx as a postmortem interval indicator was first described by Rognum et al (1991). Vitreous humor has also been analysed for free amino acids.

Small organic molecules, such as short chain volatile fatty acids (C₂–C₅), were the primary focus of early studies into the chemistry of decomposition in the mid-late postmortem interval. The analysis of VFAs has typically been carried out using gas chromatography (GC).

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) associated with decomposition have long been used as a means of training cadaver dogs to aid in the detection of clandestine graves. VOCs evolved from a decaying body were analysed by TD/GC–MS to provide a chemical profile of decomposition.

Though not directly related to the estimation of postmortem interval, one of the most widely studied decomposition products is adipocere. While FTIR analysis has been useful in studying trends, analysis of adipocere using GC–MS has allowed a more detailed understanding of its composition. [13]

The determination of the date of death from bone remains is of scientific interest but also has important legal implications. The

establishment of the postmortem interval (PMI) is a very complex problem because of the great number of intrinsic factors that may alter the normal course of postmortem change, such as the age, sex, constitution and previous physiological and pathological states of the subject, and external factors.

The mineral phase of bone is constituted of poorly crystalline hydroxylapatite, characterized by the presence of numerous foreign ions. Biological apatites can exhibit different chemical compositions, crystallinity and stability depending on several factors. Among these factors, crystal size has an important role because it determines the surface area and, as a consequence, influences the stoichiometry and the solubility properties of biological apatites.

As bone decays, the organic matter undergoes disintegration, which leads to the formation of simple chemical substances. In this respect, the variation in the proteins and amino acids found in bones has been studied by several authors. Modifications of the bone lipids have also been studied. Of special importance are techniques used to study the mineral components of bone since these, too, vary with time. Variations in nitrogen concentration and other components such as iron, lead, zinc, phosphorus, magnesium and potassium contents have also been studied. Strontium and barium in human bones are commonly used as indicators for varying diets in paleodietary studies.

Castello.M.J (2007), et.al, studied potassium, sulphur, nitrogen, urea, total protein, phosphorus, and some X-ray diffraction (XRD) parameters related to the degree of crystallinity of the mineral component in medullar and cortical bone zones to establish which of the two provide the most useful information for calculating the PMI. The study inferred a high concentration of nitrogen and urea in the medullar bone and a high sulphur, potassium, and protein value in cortical zone. Researchers propose the use of both XRD and biochemical analyses (especially of urea, potassium and sulphur) particularly in the cortical zone of the bone to be an alternative method for dating osseous remains. [14]

For almost half a century it has been recognized that there are pronounced biochemical changes post-mortem, especially in the brain. Post-mortem interval affects the proteome, in some cases within minutes of death.

A study was designed to assess the influence of high energy head-focused microwave irradiation and the postmortem interval on measurements of the mouse brain proteome.

Difference gel electrophoresis was used to compare mouse brain protein levels in animals killed by decapitation, where the tissue was held at 25°C for selected time intervals post-mortem, and by high-energy head-focused microwave irradiation followed by immediate resection. Microwave-mediated killing was used because it comprehensively snap-inactivates enzymes while largely retaining brain cytoarchitecture. The aim of this study was to establish the influence of two key factors on the brain proteome: (i) the method of death and (ii) the post-mortem interval. Using two dimensional difference gel electrophoresis for protein separation and MALDI-TOF MS identification of proteins, researchers inferred the use of high-energy head-focused microwave killing, when compared with decapitation, minimizes the potential for post-mortem changes in brain protein levels, including post-translational modifications.

Findings of the study indicate that the large majority of brain proteins are stable during a post-mortem interval of up to 4 h at 25°C. However, several proteins thought to be of critical importance to synaptic and/or neurological function were found to

change rapidly after death, and many of these were phosphoproteins. [15]

A study by Tavichakorntrakool et.al (2008), performed a serial analysis of post mortem changes in proteome profile, histology, electrolytes (K, Mg and Ca) contents, water composition and LDH enzyme activity in vastus lateralis muscle.

The study aimed to obtain preliminary data that could be used as guidance for the determination of the longest postmortem interval for reliable proteomic, histological, chemical and biochemical studies.

Using the above mentioned set of markers, researchers were able to demonstrate that storing the muscle samples at 4°C could delay some of the post mortem changes, which occur more rapidly at 25°C. [16]

CONCLUSION:

Biomarkers are important biochemical parameters that are used to study various aspects of diseases and also used to study the postmortem changes that take place in human body after death.

Biomarkers are now an integral part of disease diagnosis and treatment of diseases. New biomarkers when discovered should be properly validated taking into consideration the various aspects of age, gender, stage of disease etc that may be a cause of variation. Better techniques for discovery and validation of various biomarkers should be developed so that biomarkers with desired characteristics can be developed and used to study the desired characteristic.

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